

OVARIAN CANCER INCIDENCE RATE IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Relevance: according to the 2022 statistics of the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center for Oncology and Radiology, ovarian cancer ranks 7th in the structure of total cancer in the Republic of Uzbekistan, and the incidence of ovarian cancer is 2.9 per 100,000 population. Among the female population of the country, ovarian cancer ranks 3rd after breast cancer and cervical cancer, and is 5.8 per 100,000 female population. In 2022, 1,033 patients with ovarian cancer were diagnosed for the first time. Of these, 14.7% of cases were actively detected during preventive examinations. The proportion of morphological confirmation of ovarian cancer in patients is 95.0%. In 10% of patients with ovarian cancer, the development of the disease is associated with the presence of certain hereditary syndromes. Hereditary breast and ovarian cancer syndromes associated with mutations in the BRCA genes are widespread.

Purpose of the study: the most common disease among the population of the Republic of Uzbekistan is analysis of ovarian cancer incidence rates.

Materials and methods: primary statistical data provided by the "Collected Information and Analysis" department under the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the national clinical protocol on the nosology "Ovarian Cancer" were used.

Results: The data on the number of patients initially registered with a diagnosis of ovarian cancer in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2022-2024 are as follows. In 2022, this indicator was 184 in Tashkent, 97 in Fergana, 17 in Syrdarya, 30 in Navoi, and 33 in Jizzakh. In 2024, this indicator was 225 in Tashkent, 115 in Fergana, 27 in Syrdarya, 20 in Navoi, and 32 in Jizzakh. The primary incidence rate of ovarian cancer was 1,033 per 100,000 population in 2022, 991 in 2023, and 1,131 in 2024.

Conclusions: an analysis of the incidence rates of ovarian cancer among the population of the Republic of Uzbekistan was conducted based on data from 2022-2024. According to it, it was found that the incidence rates are high in Tashkent city and Fergana region, and low in Syrdarya, Navoi and Jizzakh regions.